

Titanium Dioxide/Graphene-Based Nanocomposites as Photocatalyst for Environmental Applications: A Review

Baji Baba Shaik,^[a] Naresh Kumar Katari,^{*[a]} Jayaprakash Kanijam Raghupathi,^[b] Sreekantha B Jonnalagadda,^{*[a]} and Surjyakanta Rana^{*[a, c]}

Nanostructured-based photocatalysts have always exhibited the potential to solve various environmental issues resulting from global urbanization and industrialization. The creation of nanostructured materials has given humans access to various techniques for treating the numerous inorganic and organic contaminants found in wastewater from multiple sources. Due to their exceptional photocatalytic activity, semiconductor materials, among various other materials have different environmental uses. Studying nanocomposites of titanium dioxide (TiO₂) and carbon-based material, particularly graphene-based material, is one of the burgeoning research areas of visible-light-driven photocatalysts. It has been demonstrated that the combination of graphene-based material with titanium dioxide is more successful than titanium dioxide alone in photo-

catalysis. TiO₂/graphene-based nanocomposites stand out due to their superior physical and chemical characteristics, such as their moderate band gap, high specific surface area, non-toxic, low cost, high corrosion resistance, high photoactivity, stability, and ease of handling in various configurations. Designing high-performance TiO₂/graphene-based photocatalysts has drawn more and more attention. This study has evaluated TiO₂/graphene-based nanocomposites for photocatalytic environmental applications from 2022 to 2024. These nanocomposites' diverse preparation methods have been discussed. The recent discoveries in TiO₂/graphene-based nanocomposite composites and their uses in photocatalysis, such as wastewater treatment to remove contaminants and photoconversion of CO₂ into renewable fuels are also briefly discussed in this review.

1. Introduction

Environmental pollution and global warming significantly impact the health of people, animals, and plants.^[1] Pollutants frequently enter natural water sources due to rapid industrial growth and negatively affect water quality.^[2,3] Volatile organic compound (VOC) and hazardous pollutant emissions have grown during the past few decades, along with the constant expansion and development of pharmaceutical and chemical industries.^[4] The quality of water bodies is impacted by anthropogenic activities such as the oil and automobile industries, paints, pharmaceuticals, wood and coal combustion, food processing, petroleum refining, other manufacturing processes, vehicle exhaust emissions, etc.^[5] The most dangerous industrial pollutants in the environment can be classified as either naturally occurring or anthropogenic, depending on their source. The primary sources of anthropogenic pollutants are different industrial processes and the combustion of materials. Natural gas, coal, and oil are used to meet the world's energy needs. These release significant quantities of harmful gases into the atmosphere, causing climate change and global warming.^[6,7]

According to the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA), natural gas is the cleanest source of fossil fuels,

mostly because it contains methane. Coal and oil have significantly more complicated molecules than natural gas does. When burned, they release toxic fumes with greater carbon, nitrogen, and sulfuric oxide levels. The tropospheric ozone layer has been affected by the toxic gas emissions and pollutants associated with transportation (i.e., greenhouse gases), which have contributed to global warming^[8] and environmental catastrophes.^[9] A common molecule that contributes to nitrogen-related pollution is ammonia.^[10,11] Numerous organic and inorganic toxins are released into water reservoirs due to industrialization, agriculture, and other human activities.^[12,13] The number of harmful substances in the water bodies and the inadequate sewage treatment at the source both reduced the freshwater quality. Because they make up a sizable group of anthropogenic chemicals and account for more than 800,000 tons of global annual production, synthetic dyes require special attention.^[14–16] An estimated third of these are discharged into receiving waters each year via industrial effluent, which can harm photosynthesis and dissolved oxygen (DO) concentration, leading to traumatic ecological crises that harm the environment and human health.^[17,18]

As a result, even minimal exposure to inorganic, organic, and textile contaminants is thought to pose a risk to both people and animals. It is now urgent and of worldwide significance to treat wastewater to eliminate and recover these toxins.^[19,20] Several approaches have been reported and applied to analyse these pollutants, including chemical precipitation, flotation, ion exchange, adsorption, coagulation, and membrane filtration.^[21,22] However, adsorption via nanocomposite materials has gained much interest because of their high selectivity and chemical and thermal stability compared with other materials. There are benefits and drawbacks to the many methods of producing different products, including photocatalytic, electrochemical, and thermochemical reactions. One of the finest methods for making renewable energy sources that lower global warming is photocatalytic water splitting under light illumination.

The ability to convert solar energy into chemical energy makes photocatalysis a cutting-edge and ground-breaking technology. Using photocatalysis, numerous processes, including hydrogen production, water purification, pollutant degradation, carbon dioxide reduction, photodynamic therapy, and

[a] B. B. Shaik, Dr. N. K. Katari, Prof. S. B Jonnalagadda, Dr. S. Rana
School of Chemistry and Physics, College of Agriculture, Engineering and
Science, Westville Campus University of KwaZulu-Natal, P Bag X 54001,
Durban 4000, South Africa
E-mail: KatariN@ukzn.ac.za
Jonnalagaddas@ukzn.ac.za
Surjyakanta.rana@tnuni.sk

[b] J. K. Raghupathi
Department of Food Science, Purdue University, West Lafayette, Indiana
47906, USA

[c] Dr. S. Rana
FunGlass – Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass,
Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Trenčín 91150, Slovakia

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Baji Baba Shaik received his master's degree in Pharmaceutical Chemistry from Mahatma Gandhi University, Nalgonda, India, in 2019. Currently, he is pursuing the PhD degree in Pharmaceutical Chemistry at College of Health Science, University of KwaZulu Natal, Durban, South Africa. His current research interest is focused on the design, synthesis of novel heterocyclic derivatives as potential antitubercular and anticancer agents.

Dr. Naresh Kumar Katari is currently working as an Analytical Research Scientist in CHEMTEX Environmental Laboratories, USA, and Honorary Research Fellow, UKZN, SA (2021–2027). He has total 17 years of teaching and research experience. He was awarded University gold medal (M.Sc. Chemistry-2006) and PhD in Chemistry from JNTU, Hyderabad, India. He visited (3 times-2018, 2019, and 2022) University of Kwazulu-Natal, Westville Campus, SA, and visited (2 times-2020 & 2024) ScieGen Pharmaceuticals Inc, New York, USA, as part of research collaboration. He was also awarded Best researcher award-19 by GITAM. 10 Scholars completed their Ph.D. studies and 2 Scholars were submitted. Four Projects were funded by SEED Grant-GITAM and BRNS, India (worth of 65 Lakhs). With over 1976 citations, H-index of 24, i-10 index of 61, he has published 200+ research articles and reviews in many reputed and high-impact journals. He also has published 5 Books, 13 Book Chapters, 23 patents and Filed 2 patents. He also reviewed more than 140 manuscripts as a reviewer.

Jayaprakash Kanijam Raghupathi possesses approximately 17 years of extensive experience in Analytical Development, Quality Control, and Quality Assurance within the pharmaceutical industry. His areas of expertise include the development and validation of analytical methods, comprehensive oversight of raw materials, in-process, finished, and stability samples, extractable and Leachable assessments, and ensuring compliance with cGMP/GDP

standards. He is currently pursuing a Ph.D. in Analytical Chemistry from Acharya Nagarjuna University (ANU), India. Additionally, he serves as a visiting scholar at Purdue University, USA, where he specializes in Analytical Method Development and Validation utilizing a variety of analytical techniques such as LC-MS, GC-MS, HPLC, UPLC, and GC for pharmaceutical and bioactive components.

Prof. Sreekantha Babu Jonnalagadda has been a Senior Professor of Chemistry at the University of KwaZulu-Natal (UKZN), since 2003. He is an elected Fellow of the University of KwaZulu-Natal (2012), South African Chemical Institute (2014), African Academy of Sciences (2015), and A.P. Academy of Sciences, India (2017). With over 8500 citations and an H-index of 43, Prof Jonnalagadda published 430+ research articles and reviews in many reputed and high-impact journals. He is consistently among the leading researchers at the University of KwaZulu-Natal and was the top researcher in 2017. His research interests include green chemistry, heterogeneous catalysis, value-added conversions, and water chemistry

Dr. Surjyakanta Rana works as a senior researcher at FunGlass in Slovakia. He previously served as a visiting scientist at Friedrich Schiller University Jena, Germany (2023). He worked as a Marie Skłodowska-Curie postdoctoral scholar in the Department of Chemistry at the University of Antwerp in Belgium, from 2019 to 2021. Between 2013 to 2017, he was a postdoctoral researcher at the Department of Chemistry at the University of KwaZulu-Natal in Durban, South Africa. He has published 58 peer-reviewed research articles and two book chapters. He works as an editor, associate editor, or guest editor for many scientific journals. His latest research focuses on 3D printing materials, MOFs, and nanocomposites for energy and environmental applications.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of semiconductor photocatalysis.

photoelectric sensing.^[23–25] To date, numerous semiconductor catalysts, including CuCrO_2 , SrTiO_3 , TiO_2 , ZnO , ZnS , CdS , Ni/KTaO_3 , Fe_2O_3 , WO_3 , MoO_3 , ZrO_2 , and SnO_2 , have been utilized to remove contaminants from wastewater.^[26] TiO_2 has captured the attention of photocatalysis research due to its excellent catalytic effectiveness, stability, and nontoxicity. However, numerous TiO_2 alterations have been created, examined, and documented.^[27,28] The TiO_2 's photoactivity was first discovered between 1932 and 1934, and then in 1938, TiO_2 was utilized as a photobleaching agent for dyes, which was then referred to as a photosensitizer. Following its development in 1969, TiO_2 was first applied for photocatalysis in 1956.^[29] The current statistical analysis shows that since 2000, there have been significantly more studies on TiO_2 photocatalysis because of its distinctive features. The period of photocatalysis began in 1972 when Fujishima and Honda, employed a TiO_2 electrode in an electrochemical cell to produce water dissociation even without applying an external voltage,^[30] discovered the water redox reaction under UV illumination. More study was done in this area by Schnauzers et al., who used titania coated in catalytic concentrations of platinum (Pt) and/or rhodium (Rh) to observe photocatalytic water breakdown.^[31] The fundamentals of semiconductor photocatalysis are shown in Figure 1. These ground-breaking investigations stimulated more photosynthetic synthesis, conversion, and solar energy storage research.

Due to its low cost, nontoxicity, stability, appropriate bandgap, and high quantum efficiency properties, TiO_2 is a widely used semiconductor photocatalyst.^[32] In TiO_2 , electrons are promoted from the valence band (VB) to the conduction band (CB) when exposed to light (Figure 1). This results in an electron vacancy or hole in the VB. However, this only happens when the photon's energy is greater than or equal to the bandgap energy of the photocatalyst.^[33] Additionally, the TiO_2 photocatalyst's bandgap energy 3.2 eV ($\lambda = 385$ nm) for anatase and 3.0 eV ($\lambda = 410$ nm) for rutile form causes photoexcitation in response to UV radiation.^[34]

The electron-hole pair in the TiO_2 photocatalyst can then proceed through a series of reactions; the CB electrons interact with

molecular oxygen to generate superoxide radical anions ($\text{O}_2^{\bullet-}$), and the VB holes support the oxidation process of water and hydroxide ions to generate hydroxyl radicals.^[35,36] The radicals formed can further participate in several reactions as a result of TiO_2 -mediated photocatalysis, such as reactions such as nitrogen fixation,^[37] hydrogen gas generation,^[38] CO_2 reduction,^[39] and pollutant decomposition.^[40] When pollutants (such as Rhodamine B (RhB), Congo red (CR), methyl orange (MO), methylene blue (MB), or other dyes) are present, VB holes and CB electrons immediately interact with the contaminants and lead to pollutant mineralization due to water and dioxygen radical formation.^[41]

Here, we have highlighted the key aspects and principal characteristics of TiO_2 /graphene nanocomposites for the effective decomposition of hazardous substances in water and wastewater, acknowledging the current significant interest in this area. A concise introduction of the fundamentals of photocatalysis utilizing TiO_2 is presented, followed by an analysis of the essential aspects influencing the application of TiO_2 or graphene oxide as photocatalysts. We have also addressed the synthetic methods for preparing of TiO_2 /graphene nanocomposites. Finally, this review offers a comprehensive overview of TiO_2 /graphene photocatalysts, including the current status, insights, advancements, progress, challenges, and future prospective applications.

Moreover, how TiO_2 and graphene interfacial charge transfer adjusts visible light activity, lessens obliteration of photogenerated charge carriers, and how TiO_2 photoactive materials are used in water treatment. Emphasis is placed on various methodologies and approaches to improve the interfacial interaction among TiO_2 and graphene-based material in their mixtures, including customizing exposed facets and shapes, TiO_2 crystal phases, defect engineering, and doping in graphene-based nanosheets. This semiconductor-graphene potential uses and actual difficulties in commercializing it are also covered.

2. Affecting the TiO_2 Photocatalysis

Photocatalysis is one of the most often used environmentally friendly, long-lasting solutions.^[42,43] Numerous studies have been done, and some are currently in the application stage in semiconductor photocatalysis-based applications, such as water splitting, solar cells, bacterial disinfection, photodynamic therapy, and primarily, for removing environmental toxins. Titanium dioxide (also known as titanium or TiO_2) has been one of the most extensively researched semiconductor photocatalysts in this field for a decade^[25,44] because of its acceptable band gap (anatase TiO_2 : 3.2 eV), chemical stability, and nontoxicity. TiO_2 nano-photocatalysts have a greater specific surface area in comparison to bulk TiO_2 , which increases their effective photocatalytic activity under practical circumstances.^[45]

The photocatalytic activity of TiO_2 is influenced by its physicochemical, chemical, and optoelectronic characteristics. The synthetic pathway, reaction parameters (precursors, solvent, time, calcination temperature, pH, etc.), and experimental settings (illumination power, pH, concentration, etc.) all affect these

Property	Graphene	Reduced Graphene Oxide
Structure	Monolayer of sp ² -hybridized carbon atoms arranged in a hexagonal lattice, with absent of oxygen functional groups.	Partially reduced form of graphene oxide, with some residual oxygen groups and defects.
Synthesis	Synthesized by using chemical vapour deposition (CVD), exfoliation, or liquid-phase exfoliation methods.	Obtained by the reduction of GO via chemical or thermal reduction techniques.
Electrical Conductivity	High electrical conductivity due to an uninterrupted sp ² network.	Lower conductivity than graphene due to residual oxygen groups and lattice defects.
Surface area	High surface area but lacks functional sites for chemical interactions.	High surface area with active sites, facilitating interactions in composite materials.
Mechanical strength	High mechanical strength and flexibility due to its defect-free structure.	Lower strength and flexibility due to structural defects from residual oxygen groups.
Photocatalysis	Enhances the electron mobility in composites and improve structural strength.	Enhances photocatalytic efficiency by reducing electron-hole recombination and adsorbing pollutants.

features.^[46,47] Crystal lattice, crystal phase, exposed crystal facets, degree of crystallinity, interface, surface sites, specific surface area, porosity, size, composition, lattice defects, and geometry are some of the primary TiO₂ attributes that the synthesis process can change.^[48,49] The most important variables affecting its photocatalytic activity are its morphology, crystal phase, pore size, dopants, cocatalysts, active sites, and band gap.

2.1. Morphology

The TiO₂ photocatalyst morphology influences the photogenerated charge carriers' separation and the type of defects formed during synthesis. TiO₂ nanomaterials have a high surface area-to-volume ratio, which increases the number of active sites. As a result, such nanostructured photocatalysts with a larger surface area display enhanced photocatalytic activity.^[50] Different TiO₂ nanostructures, including nanoparticles (NPs), nanorods, nanotubes, nanoflakes, nanosheets, and quantum dots can be created using the sol-gel, flame hydrolysis, solvothermal, hydrothermal, direct oxidation, chemical vapour deposition, sonochemical, water-in-oil, chemical vapour deposition, and micro-emulsion processes.^[51,52] The morphology and geometry of the TiO₂ nanomaterials can also change the optoelectronic properties, which can alter the charge separation/transfer and shift the absorption spectrum. Table 1 lists the benefits and drawbacks of the most popular techniques.

2.2. Surface

The surface chemistry, reactive facets, interfaces, and active sites significantly impact the efficiency of TiO₂ photocatalysts.^[53] The efficiency of the photocatalyst is increased by the improvement of proton transport between the various contacts.^[54] Numerous modification techniques, such as doping, co-doping, surface coating, sensitization, defect creation, and heterojunction formation using functional nanomaterials (graphene-based nanomaterials, oxides, quantum dots, macromolecules, etc.), have been investigated to increase the photocatalytic activity.^[55]

2.3. Light

Due to its greater band gap and TiO₂'s UV activity, one of the limitations of TiO₂'s photocatalysis is its small photocatalytic area. To further modify the electronic structure of TiO₂ photocatalysts and turn them into visible light active photocatalysts, nanostructures, doping, sensitive doping, co-doping, heterogeneous formation, semi-conductor coupling, oxygen vacancy formation, cocatalyst loading, and defect engineering can be used.^[56,57] The band gap alteration enhances the photocatalytic activity and makes it easier for photoinduced charges to migrate and separate.^[27]

2.4. Phase

With distinct band gap energies of 3.2, 3.0, and 3.1 eV, respectively, titanium dioxide nanoparticles primarily feature three structures: anatase, which is stable at low temperatures, rutile, which is stable at higher temperatures, and brookite, which is typically found in minerals with an orthorhombic crystal structure.^[58] The relative stability of these three phases varies with particle size and is stable at ambient and low pressures. Recent research has demonstrated that the phase composition and oxidant affect the photoactivity of organic decomposition; for instance, when comparing the performance of various crystal forms, rutile demonstrated the highest photocatalytic activity toward H₂O₂, and anatase showed the most increased photocatalytic activity toward O₂. A promising photocatalyst should be affordable, non-toxic, photostable, physiologically and chemically inert, and able to utilize visible and/or near-UV light.

Significantly, anatase TiO₂ has demonstrated the highest photocatalytic activity than the other forms due to its larger negative CB edge potential, which permits the generation of higher potential energy electrons upon photoexcitation.^[59] The anatase form exhibits higher crystallinity, more specific surface area, and higher stability and is nontoxic compared to the rutile and brookite forms. Although samples comprising mixes of anatase and rutile showed excellent levels of photocatalytic activity, rutile alone has only sometimes been reported to be

active in the photolysis of organic compounds in aqueous solutions. Due to the difficulties in producing pure brookite, brookite is of much less interest as a semiconductor photocatalyst in terms of its function in the photocatalytic activity of titania nanopowder.^[34,60] Additionally, according to specific research, mixed phases of TiO₂, such as anatase-rutile and anatase-TiO₂(B), performed better than a single phase of TiO₂.^[61,62]

Still, TiO₂'s most significant weakness in finding high-output commercial applications are its UV light absorption and high recombination rate. Different strategies are investigated to overcome the constraints and increase light absorption into the visible area while reducing recombination. The most crucial method used to make TiO₂ visible light photoactive is bandgap engineering, which entails lowering the bandgap of TiO₂ by adding other materials through doping (with metals and nonmetals) or by self-doping or co-doping through unique preparation techniques.

3. Doping

Numerous techniques have been used to examine how to stop the recombination of electron-hole pairs photogenerated by undoped TiO₂. The higher sensitivity towards the visible spectrum is accomplished by altering the TiO₂'s electrical configuration through doping.^[63] Any species of TiO₂ doped promotes the transfer of its unique material chemistry. A high degree of crystallinity is primarily due to the crystal size and greater specific surface area, which improves the photocatalytic activity and reduces the photogenerated charge separation of e⁻/h⁺ pair recombination.^[64,65] The TiO₂ photocatalytic treatment is frequently investigated and explored because the typical efficiency of light exploitation by titanium dioxide is lower because the electron and hole recombination generally converts the radiation into thermal energy. The reduced efficiency is caused by the fact that only photons with UV or shorter wave-length energy sources may be absorbed due to photon dispersion and the inherent physical characteristics of TiO₂. TiO₂ modification is therefore viewed as one of the technologies with the most potential for use in future photocatalytic processes. One of the best ways to increase visible light absorption is by heteroatomic doping, which lowers the band gap.^[66] The rate of electron/hole recombination is decreased. Additionally, altering or doping TiO₂ with nonmetal, metal, or anions can result in improved TiO₂ efficiency, maximal photocatalytic activity, and faster charge separation times. There are several nonmetallic dopants have been reported, including carbon,^[67] nitrogen (N),^[68] sulfur (S),^[69] boron (B),^[70] iodine (I),^[71] N/F-doped TiO₂,^[72] l-amino acids (C–N or C–N–S doped)-TiO₂,^[73] C–N–TiO₂/CNT composites,^[74] TiO₂-graphene based composites etc.

4. Graphene and Graphen Oxide

Since its discovery, the “dream material” known as graphene, an sp²-hybridized carbon sheet, has been applied repeatedly in the domains of science and engineering.^[75,76] Designing heterogeneous semiconductor/graphene composite photocatalysts is one of graphene's most alluring uses.^[34] The semi-conductor oxide photocatalytic activity can be changed thanks to the adaptability of graphene-based materials, a well-known contender with a two-dimensional structure, mechanical strength, outstanding thermal conductivity, and exceptional electron flexibility.^[77] Additionally, the zero band gap and high electron mobility of graphene serve as an electron reservoir, lowering the amount of electron-hole pair recombination required for a perfect photosensitizer. In addition, graphene stands out as a favorable framework for securing TiO₂ NPs and having the potential to adsorb contaminants due to its large Brumauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) surface area.^[45,78] Most photocatalyst systems have poor quantum efficiency, poor stability, and poor activation by visible light. The difficulty lies in creating heterogeneous photocatalysts under visible light. In this sense, graphene-based semiconductor composites can overcome these limitations, leading to increased visible absorption and photocatalytic activity.

Reduced graphene oxide (RGO) exhibits similar properties such as optoelectronic, mechanical, and conductive characteristics with natural graphene due to its heterogeneous structure, which includes a basal plane that resembles graphene but is also adorned with structural defects and populated with regions that contain oxidized chemical groups.^[79,80] The characteristics comparable to graphene render reduced graphene oxide an exceptionally sought-after material in various sensor, biological, environmental, catalytic, optoelectronic, and storage applications. Graphene oxide (GO) exhibits restricted photocatalytic activity; nevertheless, it markedly improves photocatalytic systems when combined with conventional photocatalysts such as TiO₂ or ZnO.^[81,82] The structure of GO, abundant in oxygen-containing functional groups, facilitates its role as an electron acceptor, hence mitigating electron-hole recombination, a prevalent issue in photocatalysis that diminishes efficiency. Furthermore, GO's extensive surface area offers ample sites for pollutant adsorption, facilitating the proximity of target molecules to the active catalyst. When reduced to generate reduced graphene oxide (rGO), the material exhibits enhanced electrical conductivity while preserving certain functional groups, which further facilitates pollutant degradation. In composite photocatalysts, GO or RGO facilitates efficient electron transport and enhances light absorption, hence augmenting photocatalytic performance and rendering these materials highly effective for pollutant removal in environmental applications.

When exposed to visible and ultraviolet light, RGO greatly increases photocatalytic redox capacity as an efficient co-catalyst with TiO₂.^[83] It surpasses the electron-hole recombination rate due to its greater electronic mobility, which enables the efficient separation of photogenerated electrons. However, GO or RGO enhances the photocatalytic degradation process because

Figure 2. Activation of TiO_2 -graphene-based composite in presence of UV and visible light.^[71]

of the π - π interaction with organic dyes and the formation of hydrogen bonds with organic contaminants.^[84]

5. Methods for Preparing TiO_2 /Graphene-Based Composite

By adding additional active sites for redox processes, graphene-based material as a hybrid with TiO_2 nanocomposites (i) improves the catalyst surface area; (ii) increases transparency, which aids in the redshift of the photoabsorption region. The composites (iii) lessen overall exciton recombination and (iv) increase the utilization of visible light. Graphene-based material collects photoelectrons due to its high conductivity value, which results in high charge carrier transfer.^[78] Charge carriers are created on the catalyst's surface by exposure to UV or visible light (Figure 2). Due to its favorable Fermi level position, the aromatic graphene's VB holes reduce electron recombination when photoelectrons are injected from the CB of TiO_2 . Here, graphene-based materials act as an electron reservoir. When the electrons on the carbon-based graphene material's surface electron interact with the adsorbed or dissolved oxygen, superoxide radicals are formed. These radicals are involved in photocatalysis.^[85] Increased carrier mobility also facilitates electron transfer, thus increasing the total effectiveness of several photocatalytic applications.^[86]

There are several techniques have been reported to synthesize TiO_2 -graphene-based nanocomposites.^[87,88] Out of different approaches, the most used synthesis methods are (i) sonication method,^[89] or (ii) hydrothermal method,^[90] solvothermal processes,^[91] sol-gel method,^[92] electrodeposition,^[93] etc. for the synthesis of TiO_2 /graphene based composite.

5.1. Sonication

Sonication is a common technique used in the lab to disseminate nanoparticles throughout the polymer matrix. In this process, ultrasonic radiation is used to mix up the nanoparti-

cles in the polymer matrix. An ultrasonic bath or horn/probe, sometimes called a sonicator, is used to perform it. Nowadays, different kinds of materials are also synthesized via this technique. Since graphene-based materials such as GO must be exfoliated before being added to an aqueous or organic solution, mixing and sonication are needed to create TiO_2 /GO composites (Figure 3).^[89] Due to its simplicity, this procedure is well known. The TiO_2 /GO composite made using this method included a UV-assisted photocatalytic reduction step to produce TiO_2 -partially reduced graphene oxide (TiO_2 /RGO).^[94]

5.2. Sol-Gel Method

The sol-gel method is the most extensively used to achieve intimate mixing and chemical interaction of graphene-based material (GO) and TiO_2 . (Figures 4) The GO nanosheets with the titanium alkoxide precursors have excellent water solubility and hydrogen bonding properties, and their surface hydroxyl groups can form oxo or hydroxo bonds with metal centres. Due to alkoxide hydrolysis, the TiO_2 nanocomposites prepared via the sol-gel method possess oxo- or hydroxo-bridging. Finally, dispersion via hydroxo-bonded GO sheets forms a sol that changes into a gel-like biphasic structure by adding GO.^[95] The process does not need high temperatures or pressures and is favourite for its controllability, reliability, and economic cost. The most commonly used titanium alkoxide species used in the preparation of TiO_2 /GSs nanocomposites were TiCl_4 , TiCl_3 , TiF_4 , $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{TiF}_6$, $\text{Ti}(\text{SO}_4)_2$, $\text{Ti}(\text{OPri})_4$, $\text{Ti}(\text{OBU})_4$, and titanium peroxy-complexes.^[91]

5.3. Hydrothermal and Solvothermal Methods

In solvothermal and hydrothermal approaches, the overall reactions were performed under temperature and pressure reactions, typically carried out in stainless steel autoclaves at 120 °C–200 °C.^[96] Generally, the hydrothermal method has the advantage of preparing various morphologies with larger surface areas of composite materials. When these procedures are applied to create TiO_2 -graphene based composites, graphene oxide (GO) is partially reduced, generating RGO. It is also common to find changes in the titanium dioxide crystal phase.^[90] According to Zhang et al.,^[66] an RGO-P25 nanocomposite with the same crystal structure and surface area as P25 was produced by hydrothermal synthesis, and the process also reduced the original GO. Because only some P25 NPs were attached to the edges of the RGO sheets, the resulting composite structure did not represent good connections.

5.4. Microwave-Assisted Synthesis

Due to its uniform heating and faster crystallization rate than hydrothermal synthesis, the microwave-assisted synthetic approach has benefits over the latter. On graphene sheets, a homogenous distribution of TiO_2 nanoparticles with exact size and shape can be attained using a variety of in situ microwave

Figure 3. Schematic representation of TiO₂-graphene-based nanocomposites synthesis by mechanical mixing and sonication.^[89]

(NH₄)₂TiF₆, Ti(SO₄)₂, Ti(OPri)₄, Ti(OBu)₄, and titanium peroxo complexes [91].

Figure 4. Schematic diagram of the sol-gel preparation of TiO₂-graphene-based nanocomposites.^[91]

or microwave-assisted techniques.^[97] Nanocomposites made of TiO₂ and graphene were created by Rasuli et al. utilizing UV and microwave radiation.^[98] By using UV radiation to activate the TiO₂ NPs, the photoelectrons from the TiO₂ NPs were transferred to the GO layer, where they began to reduce and eventually destroy the graphene nanosheets. Advantages and drawbacks of several techniques for creating TiO₂-graphene-based photocatalysts are listed in Table 2.

6. TiO₂-Graphene-Based Composites for Wastewater treatment

TiO₂ photocatalysis has many practical applications, including wastewater treatment, microorganism inactivation/sterilization and air purification. Ideal photocatalyst implies low cost, long-term stability, eco-friendly, reproducibility, recyclability, and efficacy.^[99] Even having several advantages, TiO₂ photocatalysts do have some limitations, including limited light absorption regions due to its wide band gap, recyclability: which is vital

for recovery and separation, recombination of photogenerated carriers, less adsorption capacity, less surface area, and aggregation issues.^[100] However, the wide band-gap of TiO₂ significantly limits the reaction of photocatalytic hydrogen. Therefore, to solve these challenges, many attempts have been undertaken to develop doped TiO₂, such as *M*-TiO₂ (*M* = Ag,^[101] Pt,^[102] Fe,^[103] Sn,^[104] Ru^[105]), sulfur-TiO₂^[106] and carbon-TiO₂^[107] nanocomposites. Due to their much higher electron/hole recombination in defect sites as well as their poor thermal stability, these metal materials have low photocatalytic performance.^[108] Another disadvantage is that the materials are more expensive due to the use of costly noble metals. Compared to *M*-TiO₂ and sulfur-TiO₂ composites, carbon-doped TiO₂ is a wonderful option since it is not only less expensive than the noble metal but also has greater light absorption and conductivity, which leads to the efficient photo-degradation of pollutants.^[109] Carbon-based TiO₂ composites can exhibit strong photocatalytic activity under UV light compared to other composites. Graphene (G), one of the most widely used two-dimensional graphitic carbon compounds, has exceptional physical and chemical characteristics. Due to the synergistic interaction between the TiO₂ and graphene bases component, TiO₂/graphene-based composite materials exhibited enhanced activity compared to pure materials.^[110] Numerous research teams have worked to date to investigate the creation and potential uses of TiO₂/graphene-based nanohybrids, and the outcomes have been largely positive. TiO₂ has been modified in several ways to increase photocatalytic efficiency, repeatability, stability, recyclability, and reproducibility.^[40] Graphene-based TiO₂ nanocomposites have emerged as significant photocatalysts for the next generation of photocatalytic applications. The synergism between components in ternary photocatalysts offers substantial advantages, including multiple interfaces, greater separation and mobility of charges, less recombination of photogenerated charge carriers, prevented aggregation, high specific area, and durability.^[111,112] In the next section, we briefly address a few advantages of TiO₂-graphene based nanocomposites towards removing environmental water pollutants.

Method	Advantages	Disadvantages
Mixing and sonication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -involves rapid, intense pressures and energy. -No additives needed -Reduced the number of steps in the reaction. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Less yields -Inefficient energy
Sol-gel method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Easiest, uniform, affordable, reliable, repeatable, and controllable. -Easy to perform in the laboratory. -Required less temperature and pressure. -High purity -It can sinter at low temperatures. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Long process time -High cost for the fabrication -The formation of anatase nanocrystals requires a high temperature (about 500 °C).
Hydrothermal and solvothermal methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Provides a simple mode of operation -It may produce large, superior crystals while keeping strong control over their chemical makeup. -The capacity to create materials that are unstable close to the melting point. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Need of expensive autoclaves -The difficulty of monitoring the crystal's growth
Microwave-assisted synthesis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Selective heating -Shorter reaction time -Reaction rate acceleration. -Easy to handle 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Expensive instrument -Unsuitable for scale-up -Unfeasible for reaction monitoring

7. Water Remediation

Water remediation can be achieved by photocatalytic oxidation or reduction. Photocatalytic oxidation processes are more focused on water remediation. The photocatalytic remediation studies were directed using various metal oxides as catalysts.^[113,114] Moreover, the wide band gap metal oxides (MOs) provide good properties such as nontoxicity and confirmed stability for water. MO nanoparticles are an attractive material to be explored for water remediation. In addition, MOs offer a high nanoscale surface-to-volume ratio, which facilitates the adsorption of pollutants to the catalyst surface.^[115,116] In particular, transition MOs demonstrate outstanding photocatalytic activity for the effective decomposition of pollutants due to their ability to control structural, crystalline, and surface features.^[117–119] Typical water pollutants include industrial wastewater (pharmaceuticals, textiles, paper, etc.), and household pollutants (pesticides, detergents, chemicals, etc.) are a significant concern globally. Incorporating graphene based material into TiO₂ (TiO₂-graphene-based nanocomposites) gained broad scope as an excellent adsorbent for removing organic contaminants due to $\pi-\pi$ interaction, electrostatic attraction, visible light absorption, and greater electron mobility.^[87,120,121] TiO₂/graphene-based composites have demonstrated potential as green and sustainable photocatalysts supporting wastewater treatment technologies for organic pollutant degradation and environmental remediation.^[122] Table 2 highlights the photocatalytic degradation properties of several organic contaminants using TiO₂/graphene-based photocatalysts that were prepared using different techniques.

7.1. Photocatalytic Degradation of Pollutants with TiO₂-Graphene-Based Composites

7.1.1. Nanocomposites

A safe and simple UV-assisted photoreduction technique was used by Xin et al.^[123] to create the TiO₂-partially reduced

graphene p-n heterojunction photocatalyst. The obtained photocatalyst showed increased photocatalytic degradation and methanol removal under UV and visible light. Some interesting results have been reported due to a substantial p-n heterojunction, the narrow band gap of the photocatalyst's, and enhanced light absorption. The primary reactive species for photocatalytic oxidation under both UV and visible light irradiation were initially identified as h⁺v⁻ species and O₂⁻ radicals from the mechanism elucidation of TiO₂-graphene-based composites (Figure 5).

A seed-induced hydrothermal synthesis was used by Xuhua and colleagues^[124] to create a compelling and durian-like TiO₂/graphene-based nanocomposite for the photocatalytic desulphurization of dibenzothiophene (DBT). The photocatalyst is characterized by different characterization techniques such as SEM, TEM, XRD, and BET. They used photoelectrochemical techniques for the DBT reaction. The findings show that, compared to other research, the TiO₂ with partially reduced graphene oxide or graphene based (TiO₂-RGO) photocatalyst has higher photocurrent density, large surface area, and wide range visible light response, with the most remarkable photocatalytic desulphurisation rate reaching 83.5% to DBT. The method shows that, the hetero-junction between rutile and anatase of TiO₂ may transmit electron-hole pairs and reduce recombination and that reduced graphene-based material can effectively adsorb DBT by pi coordinates. In terms of cost overall, it is less expensive in photocatalytic desulfurization (Figure 6).

Truong and his team reported a one-pot hydrothermal synthesis of TiO₂/graphene based aerogel photocatalyst for the photodegradation of methylene blue (MB) in an aqueous solution.^[126] The synthesised nanocomposite was characterized by XRD, FTIR, SEM, TEM, UV-vis, and Raman spectroscopy. The photocatalytic activity of TiO₂/graphene-based aerogel was assessed in the photodegradation of MB. They used 20 mg of catalyst for 120 min with pH 9 for the MB degradation. Finally, 99.9% of MB was degraded after 120 min. The TiO₂/graphene-based aerogel's pore structure and volume improve MB removal

Figure 5. Methanol removal in various atmospheric conditions using ultraviolet and visible light.^[123]

Figure 6. Desulfurization of DBT by photocatalysis and stability of DM-TiO₂/RGO and analogs such as: Desulfurization rate (a); stability of the cycle (b); pH influence (c); and effect of the amount of photocatalyst (d).^[124]

through photodegradation and adsorption. The first step in the plausible photodegradation mechanism is the pi-pi interaction between the delocalized conjugated area of the graphene matrix and the aromatic ring with $-N=N-$ or $-N=C-C=C-$. Next, positively charged MB molecules stimulate electrostatic forces and cationic bonds between the functional groups of graphene-based material (Figure 7).

The nHAp/TiO₂/Graphene based ternary photocatalyst displays excellent performance with increasing dosage and time, reaching a 98% absorption of MB, providing strong evidence from UV studies.^[127] The ternary complex liberates extremely

effective radical species that exhibit extensive degradation of the MB dye to soluble products. From this, the ternary nanocomposites follow pseudo-first order kinetics, demonstrating high absorption affinities and exceptional potential to remove dyes from wastewater. Based on the above mechanism, ternary nanocomposites that absorb UV light push electrons from the lower to the upper level and create holes. Then, the O₂⁻, and OH[•] are the primary photogenic free radical species participating in the degradation process (Figure 8).

Syeda's group^[129] developed a visible-light-induced method for degrading reactive yellow 145 (RY145) using graphene-based

Figure 7. Schematic of the synthesis procedure of TiO₂/GA.^[126]

Figure 8. Photocatalytic mechanism of nHAp/TiO₂/GO.^[127]

quantum dot (GQD)-incorporated TiO₂ nanocomposite. They adopted the sol-gel strategy to prepare nanocomposite. The obtained nanocomposite was confirmed with different analytical studies, including FTIR, XRD, UV-visible spectroscopy, SEM, and EDX. The physicochemical results indicated that TiO₂-GQD, at a calcination temperature of 300 °C, improved the photocatalytic efficiency (99.3%) for RY145 dye for 30 min. Moreover, the photocatalytic reaction followed the pseudo-first-order kinetic model. The primary active species in the TiO₂-GQD was shown to be superoxide (O₂^{•-}) generated in the nanocomposite's conduction band by the photocatalytic reaction process described above. This result suggests that superoxide played a key role in the discoloration of the RY145 dye. According to the authors, the nanocomposite sustained its effectiveness until the seventh cycle, with a minor 9% performance drop in the last cycle.

Malachite green (MG) was better photodegraded by sulfur-doped TiO₂/porous graphene based nanocomposites (S-TiO₂/RGO) reported by Nguyen's team.^[131] Nanocomposite was created using the sol-gel technique. Systematic studies were carried out to determine the factors influencing the surface morphology of the samples. The S-TiO₂/RGO photocatalyst showed good photocatalytic activity towards the degradation of MG with 99.86% in 90 minutes with 30 min of adsorption equilibrium, neutral pH, and MG concentrations of 400 and 20 mg/L, respectively. In addition, the chemical oxygen demand (COD) was also examined. To separate the irradiation charge and

Figure 9. The photocatalytic degradation pathway of nitenpyram on the produced TiO₂/CLP/graphene nanocomposite is shown schematically.^[132]

speed up contact with MG molecules, RGO with an excellent specific surface area and porosity π - π conjugated system may be essential.

Ghader et al.^[132] synthesized a new TiO₂/graphene-based nanocomposite supported on clinoptilolite nanoplate via the hydrothermal method. The photodegradation of the insecticide nitenpyram was used to test the photocatalytic activity of TiO₂/graphene-based nanocomposite/ clinoptilolite nanoplate. Clinoptilolite nanoplate and graphene's microstructure, morphology, greater effective surface area, improved visible light harvesting, and charge carrier separation could be primarily blamed for this improved efficiency. In general, hydroxyl radicals were important active species for the developed photocatalyst's ability to photocatalytically degrade nitenpyram. This work offers a new method for creating more potent graphene and TiO₂-based nanocomposite materials that are supported by clinoptilolite nanoplate photocatalysts for environmental remediation.

Man et al.^[134] conducted the photocatalytic degradation of potassium butyl xanthate in a flotation plant using TiO₂/graphene based nanocomposites as catalysts. The photocatalytic nanocomposite was prepared via the hydrothermal method. For the first time, TiO₂/graphene based photocatalyst is used to treat mineral processing wastewater. This nanocomposite was well suited for degradation due to its small pore capacity, high specific surface area, and low electron-hole pair complexation rate. The best catalytic action for the breakdown of potassium butyl xanthate was found at 18% TiO₂/graphene-based material, which was determined by the photocatalytic decomposition efficiency. This work supports the creation of prospective photo- and photoelectron systems for treating effluent from actual mineral processing (Figure 9).

Altin et al.^[135] investigated the photocatalytic degradation of bisphenol A under UV light with Cu doped TiO₂ with

graphene-based (CuO-TiO₂/GO) photocatalyst. A hydrothermal method is adopted to prepare nanocomposites. GO with 10 wt% in CuO-TiO₂/GO nanocomposite has demonstrated higher bisphenol A removal, 56.5%, compared with CuO/TiO₂ (28.8%) photocatalyst under visible light after 300 min. It should be highlighted that the photocatalytic processes generated the majority of the reactive oxygen species (ROS). Exposing the CuO-TiO₂/GO to visible light allows electrons to quickly reach the composite surface, limiting the recombination of e⁻_{CB}/h⁺_{VB} pairs. Photo-generated electrons combine with adsorbed oxygen molecules to create O₂⁻ radicals, while holes react with H₂O adsorbed on the surface of CuO-TiO₂/GO or OH⁻ to make OH radicals. All of the aforementioned. BPA is degraded by OH and O₂⁻ radicals, resulting in CO₂, H₂O, and less harmful byproducts. The ternary composite has the potential to be a highly effective photocatalyst in secondary treatments that break down other organic contaminants, according to the authors.

Nidhi and coworkers^[136] reported the efficient and time-reductive degradation of MG and MB using TiO₂-graphene-based nanocomposite. Under UV visible light irradiation, this nanocomposite with a high specific surface area efficiently destroys the cationic dyes MG and MB with a percentage of 85% and 93% at 13 and 60 min, respectively. The rate constants for the MG and MB dyes in this photocatalytic degradation were 0.1291 and 0.1709 mol/L min⁻¹, respectively, and followed pseudo-second-order kinetics. Synthesized TiO₂ NPs have a bandgap of 3.07 eV, according to this study. It also demonstrates that these NPs can excite when exposed to high-energy UV radiation and generate electron-hole pairs that can react with O₂ and H₂O to form O₂⁻ and OH, respectively. The MG and MB dyes are susceptible to oxidation and mineralization by these superoxide and hydroxyl radicals. The uncomplicated, inexpensive, low-temperature, thermally more stable, and fast reaction-time photocatalyst synthesis method is the main advantage of this study.

Lei et al.^[138] illustrated TiO₂/graphene based nanocomposite for decomposing methyl orange (MO), methylene blue (MB), and rhodamine B (RhB) dyes in wastewater. These nanocomposites were created by adapting a one-step hydrothermal process. According to the results, TiO₂-6%RGO degraded 1.67 times faster than TiO₂ for MO at 15 minutes. It is attributed to graphene-based material's strong electron transfer ability and improved adsorption properties.

Usharani et al. found that under various irradiations, such as UV, visible, and sunlight exposure, a TiO₂-graphene based nanocomposite connected with the Fenton reagent provided sound photocatalytic degradation of picric acid.^[140] Among the various light irradiation circumstances, sunshine and visible light supported the existence of a RGO-incorporated TiO₂ catalyst's maximum degrading efficiency. The hydroxyl radical was generated during the Fenton-like advanced oxidation process and played an essential role in the degradation process (Figure 10).

Heltina et al.^[141] reported that the TiO₂-graphene-based photocatalyst, prepared by reflux condition for the photodegradation of phenol in the presence of visible and ultraviolet light. According to this study, the surface area, structure, and phase of the TiO₂ nanocrystals can be controlled by adding graphene to the TiO₂ nanocomposite. The results showed that thanks to

Figure 10. Degradation tests of MB in the presence of the catalyst under visible light.^[140]

its wide surface area and good crystallinity, the reflux method had demonstrated the highest percentage of phenol degradation under a mercury lamp, at 89.56%. Because of the mercury lamp's high light intensity, there are more photons covering the semiconductor surface per unit area. The hydroxyl radicals and superoxide ions (O₂^{-*}) that break down phenol are increased as a result.

Recently, Putthicha and coworkers^[142] have developed a nanocomposite film with TiO₂ and GO embedded in a polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) matrix to effectively remove perfluorooctane sulfonic acid (PFOS) and perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) from water via photocatalytic degradation approach. After three hours of heat treatment at 120 °C, the nanocomposite film containing 25 weight percent TiO₂/GO demonstrated exceptional photocatalytic efficacy by removing 95.99% of PFOS and 96.89% of PFOA when exposed to visible light. Additionally, it was discovered that the solution's pH, the amount of GO present, and the length of the heat treatment were important factors affecting the photocatalytic performance. Acidic conditions (pH 3) and the optimal GO concentration of 25 wt% being most effective.

A hydrothermal/solvothermal synthesis was used by Martina and colleagues to synthesize TiO₂@RGO nanocomposite for the photocatalytic degradation of methylene blue (MB) dye.^[143] The photocatalyst is characterized by different characterization techniques such as SEM, XRD, and BET. The results indicates that, compared to other research, the TiO₂ with partially reduced graphene oxide or graphene based (TiO₂-rGO) photocatalyst. The findings show that, compared to other research, the TiO₂ photocatalyst with 8 wt% of rGO has higher photocurrent density, large surface area, and significant photocatalytic activity rate reaching 99.20% removal of MB in 2 h.

Martina et al.^[144] conducted the photocatalytic degradation of MB and RhB dye under artificial solar-like radiation

Figure 11. The degradation efficiency of TiO₂ NRs and TiO₂ NRs/3D-GO.^[125]

using TiO₂/RGO based nanocomposites as photocatalysts. Self-assembly of the photocatalytic nanocomposite was achieved by hydrothermal technique followed by calcination treatment. With photodegradation rates of 98.1% for MB and 99.8% for RhB, the nanocomposite containing a greater percentage of rGO (TiO₂@rGO (15%)) demonstrated exceptional performance. The results, however, show that this nanocomposite catalyst had less photocatalytic activity than P-25 because of its large-layered structure, which makes it easy to recover from the aqueous medium following the photocatalytic event.

7.1.2. Nanorods-Based TiO₂ Nanocomposites

Wang et al.^[125] used hydrothermal synthesis and investigated the photocatalytic activity of TiO₂ nano-rods (TiO₂-NR)/graphene-based material in the decolorization of Acid orange 7 (AO7) dye from textile effluent. Photocatalytic investigation showed that complete decolorization of 100 mL of 150 mg/L AO7 was achieved after UV exposure for 160 min and 140 min for TiO₂-NR and TiO₂-NR/graphene-based material, respectively, which indicates effective photocatalytic activity (Figure 11).

7.1.3. Nanoparticle-Based TiO₂ Nanocomposites

Birgitta and team^[128] reported a new photocatalytic system by modifying TiO₂ via doping nonmetal elements (S and N) and different amounts of graphene based materials to form the composite. The synthesized material exhibited excellent photocatalytic degradation of dimethyl sulfide (DMS) and dimethyl disulfide (DMDS). Photocatalysts with 0.1wt%rGO/S_{0.05}N_{0.1}/TiO₂ had promising photocatalytic efficiency for DMDS and DMS. The above results concluded that reducing the band gap, increasing surface area, and relative humidity are essential in enhancing photocatalytic activity.

Wang et al.^[130] employed a new strategy for three-step electrochemical synthesis to fabricate electrochemically converted N-doped TiO₂/graphene-based (ENTG) nanoparticles, and the

photocatalytic degradation of humic acid (HA) was achieved. Under ideal conditions, there was a 92.3% increase in HA degradation. The ENTG photocatalyst demonstrated better degrading performance, stability, and recyclability than typical hydrothermally generated NTG nanoparticles. Based on adsorption and free radical oxidation, the explanation of the HA degradation mechanism shows that both •OH and •O₂⁻ radicals were produced during the process, with •OH playing the primary role in HA degradation. These findings suggest that ENTG, a robust and recyclable photocatalyst for humic acid breakdown, has significant potential for real-time applications in treating municipal wastewater (Figure 12).

Nguyen et al.^[133] studied the photodegradation of crystal violet (CV) using sulfur-doped TiO₂/graphene-based aerogel (S-TiO₂/G). The aerogel was synthesised via the coprecipitation method using Ti{OCH(CH₃)₂}₄, graphene-based material (GO), and thiourea as precursors. The S-TiO₂/G catalysts displayed enhanced photocatalytic activity. The synergistic effects between the good photocatalytic activity of the pure TiO₂ and the high adsorption capacity of the graphene-based aerogel can significantly increase the photodegradation efficiency of the nanocomposites, which can be achieved by the sharp increase in the removal efficiency to 99.85%, according to the results. In addition to specific surface area and the porous structure of graphene, aerogel can also help and participate in the adsorption process, which increases the interaction rate between catalysis centres and CV molecules. The dominant photocatalytic degradation of CV was achieved with 99.85% removal.

Ning et al.^[137] prepared TiO₂ with new porous graphene based (PG/TiO₂) nanocomposite with a highly reactive interface using TiCl₄ as the titanium source via a partial combustion strategy. The nanocomposite PG/TiO₂ displayed the concurrent result of excellent absorptivity and photodegradation activity towards tetracycline antibiotics under UV-visible light. The tetracycline removal rate was observed up to 95.5%, which is higher (25%) than P25 within 90 min. This photocatalytic improvement was credited to PG's porous structure, high surface area, and the very reactive interface between TiO₂ and PG NPs. This study investigates TiO₂-porous graphene-based nanocomposites for highly effective antibiotic removal, which may be a possible strategy to advance the solution of many environmental problems (Figure 13).

Recently, Sohel et al.^[139] reported TiO₂ with graphene based nanoparticles (TiO₂/GO) using titanium tetra isopropoxide as a precursor of TiO₂. The nanocomposite was studied for photocatalytic degradation of Congo red (CR) and methylene blue (MB) under sunlight irradiation. The TiO₂-GO nanocomposite with a 1:5% ratio had the highest efficiency, degrading CR by 85% in 60 minutes and MB by 90% in 80 min. The synthesized nanoconjugate, TiO₂-GO verified to be a minimal cost, extremely recyclable and most effective photocatalyst for the fast degradation of industrial dyes under sunlight light.

Silver-doped titanium dioxide/graphene aerogel (Ag-TiO₂/GA) was created by Truong Thi and colleagues^[145] using a straightforward hydrothermal process with varying Ag stoichiometry. Under ideal conditions of pH 6.5, 25 mg/L CV concentration, and 29 mg catalyst dose, the ATG50 sample,

Figure 12. HA removal rate for TNT, N/TNT, NTG, and ENTG, (a) in darkness, (b) under irradiation with visible light.^[130]

Figure 13. Schematic of the proposed mechanism for photodegradation toward TC by PG/TiO₂.^[137]

made with 50 mg of AgNO₃, had the strongest photodegradation performance towards CV dye, reaching up to 99.95% removal efficiency. Significant photodegradation potentials against MB (97.11%) and indigo carmine (IC) (53.22%) were also demonstrated by this catalyst, which also showed excellent reusability even after five recycling runs and a small silver release.

Fei et al.^[146] used electrophoresis and impregnation techniques to create a nitrogen-doped TiO₂/graphene/nickel foam photoelectrode in 2024. The synthetic material was used to break down MO aqueous solution in the presence of sunlight. At 10V and in the presence of sunlight, the N/TiO₂-graphene/Ni photoelectrode showed a catalytic kinetic constant of $3.96 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$, which was greater than the kinetic constants of photocatalysis and electrocatalysis alone. According to the results, light degradation and electro-Fenton oxidation work in concert because graphene improved the separation efficiency of the photogenerated charges and activated the bound electrons in N/TiO₂ to create photogenerated electron-hole pairs.

7.1.4. Nanosheet-Based TiO₂ Nanocomposites

Apisit group^[147] reported a photoactivity in converting CO₂ gas to methane and acetone using copper-TiO₂/graphene

nanosheets. The TiO₂ nanosheets were synthesized using one-step hydrothermal method in the presence of a hydrofluoric acid soft template and composited with graphene oxide and doped with copper oxide to yield desired nanocatalyst. At 100% relative humidity, the photoactivity of the nanosheets was active, producing methane and acetone at rates of 12.09 and 0.75 $\mu\text{mol h}^{-1} \text{ gcat}^{-1}$, respectively, and consuming 71.70 $\mu\text{mol/gcat}$ of TOC. Inside the two two-dimensional nanostructures, the copper-TiO₂/GO heterostructure's photoactivity was recognized. The interfaces between the graphene oxide and the nanosheets functioned as n-p heterojunctions, retaining active radicals for further reactions.

Wang et al.^[148] implemented a hydrothermal method for synthesising TiO₂-graphene-based (TiO₂-GO) photocatalysts. SEM, TEM, XRD, UV-vis, XPS, and Raman was adopted to confirm the morphology and crystallinity. Visible light was used to assess the composite's photocatalytic denitration. By achieving a 1:1 ammonia-to-nitrogen ratio, the denitration efficiency can reach 88.6%, which is 30% greater than homemade unmodified TiO₂ and 40% higher than V-Ti-W catalyst. The GO composite ratio of 1.5% holds the most incredible photocatalytic denitration performance. The mechanism analysis reveals that the photocatalytic denitration process depends on the rate at which NO is oxidised, and that the presence of NH₃ speeds up the reduction of NO₂ in the reaction.

Zhongjie reported^[149] a photocatalytic degradation activity using hyper-crosslinking porous polymer layers on TiO₂-graphene-based material as a visible light-driven photocatalyst. By increasing the specific surface area from 136 to 988 m²/g, this photocatalyst graphene surface contributes to a high adsorption and removal capacity of sulfadiazine with 54.3 mg/g, which is 15.5 times greater than that of TiO₂-graphene-based material (3.5 mg/g). Additional research on the effectiveness of photodegradation can be done for the removal of other common pollutants, including 4-chlorophenol and methylene blue. According to the aforementioned mechanism, graphene serves as a conductive backbone carbon to knit the polymer layer and enhance charge transfer, TiO₂ offers an active catalyst site for activating oxygen molecules, and the ultrathin polymer layer is in charge of sulfadiazine enrichment and visible light

Figure 14. Mechanism of photocatalytic CO₂ reduction.^[151]

absorption. It breaks down sulfadiazine by producing O₂⁻ and OH radicals. These results indicate that the porous photocatalyst shows improved absorption and photodegradation efficiency to remove typical pollutants such as sulfadiazine, 4-chlorophenol and methylene blue under visible light.

Recently, Zhang's team^[150] that TiO₂-graphene-based nanocomposites (TiO₂-rGO) can be used as a photocatalyst for the photocatalytic degradation of MO and Rh B when exposed to visible light. In this series, when exposed to visible light, TiO₂-rGO demonstrated strong photocatalytic activity for the degradation of Rh B and MO. The adsorption capabilities of TiO₂ composite are enhanced by the addition of rGO. As evidenced by adsorption in the dark, it provides conductive pathways for electron transfer for Rh B and MO, inhibiting the recombination rate of electron-hole pairs. This process results in the best catalytic activity.

7.2. TiO₂/Graphene-Based Composites for Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) Photoconversion

The primary source of climate change and global warming is CO₂ emissions from the usage of fossil fuels, which have been an issue for several decades. As a result, there is a growing interest in discovering new strategies around the world to cut CO₂ emissions. Combining graphene with TiO₂ can produce composites with exceptional qualities that combine the functions of the two components while also introducing some novel properties. Therefore, graphene-based photocatalysts present a wide range of photo-catalytic CO₂ reduction options. AgCuInS₂/G/TiO₂ quaternary nanocomposites were synthesized, and photocatalytic CO₂ reduction was studied by Zambaga et al.^[151] Under high selectivity light irradiation, the photocatalyst demonstrated outstanding photoconversion of CO₂ reduction to methanol (CH₃OH). The increased photocatalyst activity was ascribed to the components working together synergistically (Figure 14).

The nickel (Ni)/ TiO₂-graphene-based nanocomposite was created by Oscar's team^[152] and employed as a photocatalyst. Using methanol-water solutions and CO₂ reduction to methanol, Ni-NPs on a TiO₂-graphene-based GO nanocomposite demonstrated high photocatalytic efficacy in hydrogen evolution. Compared to undoped TiO₂-GO, the photocatalytic reduction of CO₂ by the nanocomposite Ni/ TiO₂-GO 3wt% showed promise. It also produced 55 μmol/h·g of methanol and boosted hydrogen evolution from 389 to 2171 μmol/h·g.

Yunju et al.^[153] published ground-breaking research on a noble metal-free photocatalyst for solar light-induced CO₂ reduction of hydrocarbons (CH₄ and C₂H₆). The hydrothermal process generated the photocatalyst with decreased TiO₂ quantum dot on a graphene sheet. The ratio of the CH₄:C₂H₆ product has altered from 3.41:1 to 1:1.62 due to the amount of graphene, which affects the conversion of CO to hydrocarbons. Compared to plain TiO₂ quantum dots, the enhanced models showed yields of CH₄ and C₂H₆ that were 2.8 and 3.7 times higher. The graphene sheet improves electron-hole separation and transmission and oxygen vacancies formation. Without additional treatment, the optimized catalyst exhibited good stability for three days. This photocatalyst is significantly more helpful for efficiently converting atmospheric CO₂ into usable fuel thanks to its high stability and photocatalytic activity.

According to Aliakbar et al.,^[154] hierarchical nanostructured GO-TiO₂-Ag₂O and GO-TiO₂-Ag₂O-Arg photocatalysts allowed for efficient CO₂ detention and selective photo-catalytic conversion into methanol. The structure of the nanomaterial is confirmed with XRD, SEM, and TEM. The predicted band gaps for GO-TiO₂-Ag₂O and GO-TiO₂-Ag₂O-Arg were 2.62 eV and 3.18 eV, respectively. When exposed to visible light, GO-TiO₂-Ag₂O-Arg and GO-TiO₂-Ag₂O exhibit strong CO₂ absorption capabilities of 1250 and 1185 mmol/g, respectively, at 10 bar and 273 K.

Irradiation, and the amounts of methanol produced by GO-TiO₂-Ag₂O and GO-TiO₂-Ag₂O-Arg were 8.154 and 5.1 μmolcat⁻¹h⁻¹. The study's key benefits are the high catalytic efficiencies and selectivity for methanol production. Additionally,

Figure 15. Reaction mechanisms for the photoreduction of CO₂ on CTNSG.^[156]

these catalysts may be utilized frequently and are stable during the photocatalytic process, which is instructive for environmental study.

Khaja et al.^[155] created a variety of Au-TiO₂ decorated N-doped graphene based photocatalysts and evaluated their CO₂ reduction photocatalytic performance in the presence of light. They characterized the highly active material via different characterization techniques such as XRD, SEM, TEM, Raman, and XPS analysis. All the above characterisation techniques confirmed the ternary composite. Studies on the catalysts using PL, TPR, EIS, and UV-vis-DRS demonstrated enhanced optical properties and smooth charge transport. The photocatalytic CO₂ reduction activity was measured under light irradiation, and the results showed that N-doped graphene-based material produced the maximum R_{electron} value of 742.39 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ in 4 hours under visible light irradiation. Future ternary hybrid solar fuel photocatalysts based on N-doped graphene are possible thanks to the presented mechanism and improved photocatalytic efficiency of ternary catalysts. Future ternary hybrid solar fuel photocatalysts based on N-doped graphene are made possible by the method shown and the enhanced photocatalytic efficiency of ternary photocatalysts (Table 3).

A study by Srinivas's group^[156] used graphene-based (GO) heterostructure and copper/TiO₂ nanosheets as a photocatalyst to convert CO₂ to fuels. TiO₂ nanosheets were synthesised using a hydrothermal method in the presence of a hydrofluoric acid (HF) soft template. The synthesized Cu/TiO₂/GO photocatalyst displayed excellent photocatalytic activity in converting CO₂ gas to fuel, such as methane and acetone. According to the study, under 100% relative humidity, methane and acetone production rates were 12.09 and 0.75 $\mu\text{mol h}^{-1} \text{gcat}^{-1}$, respectively, resulting in a total carbon consumption of 71.70 $\mu\text{mol h}^{-1} \text{gcat}^{-1}$ (Figure 15).

Wang et al.^[157] highlighted porous hyper-crosslinked polymer/TiO₂/graphene-based photocatalysts under visible-light-driven CO₂ conversion. The as-synthesized photocatalyst has an enormous surface area of 988 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$ and a high capacity to absorb CO₂ of 12.87 wt%. Without using co-catalysts made of precious metals or sacrificial reagents, this composite demonstrated outstanding photocatalytic activity, specifically for the generation of methanol (27.62 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$). This method pro-

vides fresh insight into using photocatalysts and microporous organic polymers for solar fuel conversion.

Yang et al.^[158] synthesized the TiO₂ spherical shells modified by graphene-based material to improve the photocatalytic activity for CO₂ reduction. The contact area of the double-sided modified TiO₂ photocatalyst was greatly increased, enabling more photoelectrons to be separated from both sides of the shell. The primary product of the photocatalytic reduction of CO₂ is CO, which is then detected with a small amount of CH₄. The results of the photocatalytic conversion of CO₂ into CO show that the effects of graphene-based material modification on the inner and outer walls of the TiO₂ shell appear to be mostly independent of one another.

TiO₂-graphene-based nanocomposites were created by Olowoyo and colleagues^[159] to improve CO₂ photoreduction to methanol. The results showed that the photocatalytic CO₂ reduction was improved, resulting in a methanol formation rate of 2.33 $\text{mmol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$, due to alterations in the band gap and encouraging the separation of photogenerated carriers.

Using Pt/graphene-based material wrapped TiO₂ nanotubes, Dev et al.^[160] observed improved methane generation by photoreduction of CO₂ at moderate temperature and pressure. Electrochemical anodized TiO₂ nanotubes are functionalized by chemically formed GO layers and sputtered-deposited Pt particles. At 1.8 atm pressure and 80 °C, the photoreduction activity produced an improved methane production rate of around 3.42 $\text{mmol.g}^{-1}.\text{h}^{-1}$.

7.3. Desulfurization of Fuels Using TiO₂/Graphene-Based Photocatalysts

Moslem et al.^[161] reported photocatalytic oxidative desulfurization of model liquid fuels under visible light irradiation using active Cu-impregnated graphene based material on TiO₂ nanocomposite photocatalyst. The TiO₂-graphene-based material was prepared via a hydrothermal technique, and then it underwent Cu (II) impregnation. The nanocomposite TiO₂-G-Cu 0.5 showed high photocatalytic oxidation and elimination activity toward dibenzothiophene when exposed to visible light in 0.1 ml H₂O₂. The dibenzothiophene elimination rate showed the best photocatalytic activity, which was observed up to 98.27% and was attributed to low electron/hole recombination, a high BET surface, and adequate band gap energy.

Xuhua et al.^[124] developed an effective heterostructure, compactly durian-like mixed-crystal TiO₂/graphene-based material (DM-TiO₂-RGO) using a seed-induced synthesis, including the anatase and rutile phase. The specific surface area of multiphase TiO₂/graphene-based material increased to 71.28 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$, and this novel structural development expanded the visible light response spectrum. The results demonstrate that, compared to the analogies, the DM-TiO₂-RGO photocatalysts had excellent photocurrent density, a larger specific surface area, and a more comprehensive range of visible light response. This resulted in the highest desulfurization rate of DM-TiO₂-RGO photocatalysts, 83.5% for dibenzothiophene (DBT). The electron-hole pairs can be transferred, and recombination is suppressed by the

Table 3. Photocatalytic characteristics of TiO₂/graphene-based nanocomposites towards degradation or removal of different organic pollutants.

Photocatalyst	Synthesis Method	Pollutant	Light Source	Degradation Efficiency (%)	References
TiO ₂ -graphene based material (TiO ₂ -GO)	Photoreduction	Methanol and VOC's	UV-visible light	100	123
TiO ₂ -graphene based material	Seed-induced hydrothermal	DBT	UV light	83.5	124
TiO ₂ nanorod-graphene based material	Hydrothermal synthesis	AO 7	UV light	100	125
TiO ₂ -graphene based aerogel	Hydrothermal synthesis	MB	UV light	99.9	126
TiO ₂ -graphene based material (TiO ₂ /GO)	Sonication method	MB	UV visible	98	127
S,N-TiO ₂ -graphene based material	Solvothermal method	DMS and DMDS	UV visible	38.2 and 44.1	128
TiO ₂ -Graphene based quantum dot (GQD)	Sol-gel method	RY145	UV visible	123	129
N-TiO ₂ -graphene based material	Electrochemical deposition	Humic acid	UV visible	92.3	130
S-TiO ₂ -graphene based material	Hydrothermal and ultrasonication	MG	UV visible	99.86	131
TiO ₂ -graphene based material supported on clinoptilolite nanoplate	Hydrothermal method	Nitenpyram	UV visible	98	132
TiO ₂ -graphene based aerogel	Coprecipitation	CV	UV visible	99.85	133
TiO ₂ -graphene based material	Hydrothermal method	Potassium butyl xanthate	UV visible	97.03	134
CuO-TiO ₂ -graphene based material	Hydrothermal method	bisphenol A	UV visible	56.5	135
TiO ₂ -graphene based material	Sol-gel method	MG and MB	UV visible	85 and 93	136
TiO ₂ -porous graphene-based material	Partial combustion strategy	tetracycline	UV visible	95.5	137
TiO ₂ -graphene based material	Hydrothermal method	MO, MB, and RhB	UV visible	96.9, 97.9 and 97	138
TiO ₂ -graphene based material	Sonication	CR and MB	sunlight	85 and 90	139
TiO ₂ -graphene based material	Hydrothermal method	picric acid	UV, visible, and sunlight	200 mg/L	140
TiO ₂ -graphene based material	Mechanical mixing	phenol	UV-Visible and ultraviolet lamp	89.56	141
TiO ₂ -graphene based material	Hydrothermal method	Ammonia	UV-Visible	88.6	148
TiO ₂ -graphene based material	Hydrothermal method	sulfadiazine	UV-Visible	98.4	149
TiO ₂ -graphene based material	Hydrothermal method	Rh B and MO	UV-Visible	98.00	150
Ag-TiO ₂ /graphene aerogel	Hydrothermal method	MB and IC	UV-Visible	97.11 and 53.22	145
N/TiO ₂ -graphene/Ni	electrophoresis	MO	sunlight	98	146
TiO ₂ /GO	Hydrothermal method	PVA-PFOS	UV-Visible	95.99 AND 96.89	142
TiO ₂ @rGO	Hydrothermal method	MB	UV-Visible	99.20	143
TiO ₂ @rGO	Calcination	MB and RhB	Solar-like radiation	98.1 and 99.8	144

heterojunction between anatase and rutile TiO₂, which is the mechanism by which RGO can effectively adsorb DBT.

Zhang et al.^[162] anticipated a hydrothermal technique for synthesizing of TiO₂-graphene-based material (TiO₂-RGO) and applied it to the desulfurization and oxidation of thiophene in model fuel. The absorption of TiO₂-RGO nanocomposites proved a remarkable red shift from 325 to 540 nm compared with pure TiO₂. The excellent shape and conductivity of RGO facilitate the transfer of electrons from bulk TiO₂ to the surface, which enhances the performance of PODS. According to the findings, adding graphene-based material can enhance titanium dioxide's photocatalytic activity when exposed to visible light and improve how it reacts to light. The TiO₂-RGO composite showed the highest thiophene elimination efficiency of 94.3% in 100 minutes with an RGO mass loading of 5%.

7.4. TiO₂/Graphene-Based Photocatalyst for Hydrogen Production

Edge-sulfonated graphene-based material decorated on TiO₂ (SO₃H-TiO₂-RGO) was made, according to Wang and collaborators,^[163] by first creating a covalent link between graphene and benzenesulfonic acid using a diazotization reaction, then connecting it with TiO₂ NPs to create an SO₃H-TiO₂-RGO photocatalyst. The synthesized photocatalyst was used for a hydrogen evolution reaction (HER). The results show that 197.1 μmol h⁻¹g⁻¹, which is higher than the corresponding values of 5.38 (TiO₂), 2.81 (TiO₂-RGO), and 3.40 (SO₃H-TiO₂), respectively, is the most remarkable H₂ production rate. Graphene and sulfonate ions' combined power is responsible for the increased efficiency of the photocatalyst. According to the mechanism,

UV exposure to TiO₂ stimulates the photogenerated electrons to the CB of TiO₂. Due to graphene-based material's superior electrical conductivity can then act as an electron-cocatalyst to quickly collect and easily move the photogenerated electrons to the -SO₃H groups. In the meantime, the reaction system's sulfonate ions (-SO₃⁻) of -SO₃H groups can produce H⁺ for the subsequent reduction of H⁺ by photogenerated electrons to produce hydrogen. This study offers a fresh perspective on creating high-efficiency graphene-based materials for photocatalytic hydrogen evolution.

The hydrothermal production of the TiO₂-graphene-based nanocomposite (TiO₂-RGO) and its application as a photocatalyst for the photoelectrochemical water-splitting reaction was reported. TiO₂-RGO nanocomposite was made by hydrothermal synthesis and used as a photocatalyst in an electrochemical water-splitting reaction that produced hydrogen.^[164] All the XRD, SEM, and TEM characterization results confirmed the surface structure and crystallinity of the nanocomposite. The binary mixture (TiO₂ + RGO) NPs achieved improved photocatalytic H₂ generation and stability compared to bare TiO₂ and RGO. The photocatalyst with the maximum hydrogen production is made of RGO-TiO₂(15%) nanocomposite. For efficient charge separation and transfer during the photocatalytic process, TiO₂ and RGO must have excellent stability and contact.

The Hager team described a very stable and active catalyst based on Co and TiO₂ NPs anchored on graphene based RGO sheets^[165] for use in photocatalytic hydrogen production from water splitting. The catalyst was prepared by the Hummers method, followed by pyrolysis. The Co-TiO₂-RGO nanocomposite establishes important photocatalytic activity under UV-vis light. The hydrogen evolution was recorded at 26,583 μmol g⁻¹ using a Na₂S and Na₂SO₃ solution and 22,289 μmol g⁻¹ by a MeOH in UV-vis light. These outcomes are attributed to the high conductivity of the RGO sheets, effective separation of the charge carriers, and excellent solar light absorption by the nanocomposites. A highly stable Co-TiO₂-RGO photocatalyst with high solar absorption and photocatalytic water splitting activity for H₂ generation may be made using this research's straightforward, inexpensive, and efficient technique.

The Jagadeesh team reported one-pot hydrothermal synthesis of defect-engineered TiO₂-x and graphene-based nanocomposites (TiO₂-x-RGO) and photocatalytic hydrogen production by splitting water molecules.^[166] This method incorporates natural flaws in the TiO₂ lattice and makes GO reduction easier in a single-pot reaction. The results showed that under solar illumination, the TiO₂-x-RGO photocatalyst produced hydrogen at a rate of 13.6 mmol h⁻¹ g⁻¹ cat. and at a rate of 947.2 μmol h⁻¹ g⁻¹ cat. With a photocurrent density of 117 μA cm⁻² under visible light (>450 nm). The optimal content of RGO promotes charge transfer, suppressing the electron-hole recombination problem, according to the authors' final assessment of their work.

Serafin et al.^[167] adopted hydrothermal synthesis and investigated the TiO₂-graphene based photocatalyst (TiO₂-RGO) in hydrogen production from a water-ethanol mixture under UV light. Photocatalytic investigation showed that outstanding H₂ production was obtained on TiO₂ with 10% RGO after calcination at 700 °C and exhibited the highest performance with a

hydrogen photogeneration rate of 9.5 mmol h⁻¹ g⁻¹. According to the mechanism, RGO first prevents TiO₂ from sintering, and then it prevents anatase from structurally changing into rutile. Improved hydrogen photoproduction rates result from these two factors and the accompanying electron delocalization that RGO in the TiO₂-RGO composites induces. TiO₂ is limited by its high band gap and the comparatively fast rate at which photogenerated electrons and holes recombine. Therefore, this study provides a novel and practical method for the design and synthesis of a new generation of photocatalysts for the creation of hydrogen.

The Hamza group created TiO₂ with a few-layer graphene-based nanocomposites^[168] using an easy, quick, effective, and environmentally friendly exfoliation technique. This technology was developed to improve solar-driven hydrogen production from methanol. Without the use of a co-catalyst, it was found that the nanocomposite with 0.5 and 1.0 wt% TiO₂-graphene based material evaluated a good H₂ generation rate from methanol when exposed to artificial solar light, which is 2–3 times more efficient than reference and commercial TiO₂. The authors claimed that the nanocomposites' acquired photocatalytic activity was also influenced by their surface area, shape, optical characteristics, and free electron mobility kinetics.

8. Outlook

Modern wastewater treatment techniques are now required for sustainability. Nanotechnology has been crucial in resolving scientific issues and effectively lowering toxins in wastewater from various sources. Due to their outstanding photoactivity, semiconductors have a greater significance than other materials produced. This review focuses on thoroughly examining the crucial elements of TiO₂-graphene-based nanocomposites with strong photocatalytic activity under exposure to ambient and artificial light. TiO₂ has intrinsic advantages such as commercial accessibility, high stability, and cost-effectiveness, making it suitable for environmental remediation for sewage treatment and air pollution. The synergistic characteristics of TiO₂ and graphene, which integrate TiO₂'s strong photocatalytic efficiency with graphene's extensive surface area, electronic conductivity, and capacity for charge carrier separation, have resulted in progress in pollutant remediation and the enhancement of sustainable energy applications. This review explores diverse synthesis techniques as well as modifications designed to enhance the efficiency and selectivity of these nanocomposites, highlighting their significance in pollutant degradation, water purification, and air quality enhancement. The issues surrounding charge recombination and light absorption continue to be central topics for future investigations. Enhancing these properties methods like doping, surface modification, and composite structuring is applied to increase material's photocatalytic efficiency in visible light conditions. Nitrogen-doped materials have exhibited excellent photocatalytic activity compared to sulfur doped materials. Also, copper, silver, and nickel supported photocatalysts showed significant removal of MB, RhB, and bisphenol A dyes.

Although many photocatalytic materials have lower efficiency and greater band gap energy values, this results in a smaller surface area and lower absorption rates. There are reports of TiO₂-graphene-based nanocomposites that can overcome constraints in photocatalysis to address difficulties with increased energy demand and pollution remediation. The key benefit of using graphene-based material is that it first photosensitizes TiO₂ to absorb visible light, extending the range of light that can be absorbed into the visible solar spectrum. Second, the slow charge transfer kinetics of TiO₂ are overcome by a cocatalyst that speeds up charge transit and inhibits charge recombination. Thirdly, when exposed to visible light, the material's enormous specific surface area, rapid electron mobility, and zero bandgaps accelerate the adsorption of different pollutants and photodegradation. TiO₂-graphene based material (TiO₂-GO) is reluctantly helpful for the breakdown and removal of numerous inorganic and organic pigments and pathogens from contaminated water due to their potent characteristics. These nanocomposite materials are appealing for environmentally friendly wastewater treatment procedures due to their straightforward production methods, high efficacy, and selectivity of pollutant adsorption. In addition, more study on various topics is required to meet the demands of photocatalysis in the future. To create new materials with exceptional photocatalytic characteristics, novel graphene-based photo-catalysts must be devised. In addition, there are several issues and problems with TiO₂-graphene-based photocatalysts that can be fixed with more study.

9. Challenges

TiO₂-graphene-based nanomaterial have exceptional chemical, mechanical, and electrical properties and distinctive structural traits. Due to several unique characteristics, TiO₂-graphene-based nanocomposites have a bright future in wastewater treatment. The most widely used methods for treating water are adsorption, filtration, and photodegradation. Surface modification of these nanomaterials is crucial to improving the photocatalytic activity of nanocomposites. More research is needed, particularly on their use, recyclable nature, preparation techniques, etc. TiO₂ with graphene-based hybrid material have come a long way, but the mechanism underlying the hybrids' enhanced photocatalytic activity is still a mystery. Additional theoretical and experimental research is needed to fully understand the electrical and semiconducting properties of graphene-doped materials and their photocatalytic mechanisms. It is unknown why graphene materials with non-zero band gaps, such as graphene oxide, graphene QDs, defect-rich graphene, heteroatom-doped graphene, and nanoribbons, show enhanced photocatalysis. Deep learning should be viewed as a prediction technique in light of the uncertainties in the chemical interactions between Ti—C and or Ti—O—C, the crystal structure in contact with graphene, and the amount of GO bound to TiO₂. Because a photo-composite is subject to a variety of conditions, including ionic strength, turbidity, pH levels, etc., the develop-

ment of these small components is still underway to provide a better and more stable photocatalyst. The TiO₂-graphene-based system demonstrated high photocatalytic activity in the removal of organic micropollutants (such as diclofenac, sulfamethoxazole, carbamazepine, etc.) and established regulated charge recombination. TiO₂-graphene based hybrids (TiO₂-GO) fared better at eradicating fecal coliforms and enterococci bacterial populations than water-assisted systems and recycling.

However, TiO₂/graphene-based nanocomposites have emerged as cutting-edge materials for photocatalytic systems and are frequently evaluated in a lab setting. Instead of improving the efficiency and robustness of large-scale applications, increasing the system's photocatalytic capability could disturb lab-scale experiments. Graphene-based TiO₂ photocatalysts have recently undergone pilot plant trials with real-world applications, primarily for wastewater treatment. To design and fabricate high-performance photocatalytic composites, graphene-based titania nanocomposites also pose additional difficulties, such as the analysis of microstructural features and the investigation of the mechanism of photocatalytic degradation. These materials benefit wastewater refinement, but some problems associated with defect densities and graphene network aggregation must be resolved. Agglomerating graphene layers reduces their surface area, which limits their permeability and ability to interact with pollutants. To solve these problems, researchers are looking into improvements in graphene-based nanomaterials that incorporate several functional moieties. Surface modification with different organic moieties like amine-, sulfo groups enhances graphene dispersion and minimizes agglomeration effects. The development of TiO₂-graphene-based photocatalysis is apparent at first glance.

Despite of considerable progress, the TiO₂/graphene-based nanocomposites efficacy under visible light remains inadequate, which constraining their practical use in environmental remediation. Following that, research should focus on the development of novel dopants, structural alterations, or hybrid materials to further augment the visible-light responsiveness of TiO₂. Stability and reusability are essential for practical applications; yet numerous TiO₂/graphene-based composites experience performance deterioration over time or throughout repeated cycles. Investigation into the stability of composites under diverse environmental circumstances, encompassing analyses of their recyclability and structural integrity, is essential. Whereas graphene and reduced graphene oxide (RGO) mitigate electron-hole recombination, numerous TiO₂/graphene composites continue to suffer significant charge loss, hence reducing their photocatalytic efficacy. Future study may concentrate on sophisticated structural designs or surface modifications that further reduce recombination rates and enhance charge separation efficiency, even in low-light circumstances. Improving this feature is essential for attaining greater photocatalytic rates in everyday use. The large-scale manufacture of TiO₂/graphene-based composites is both complex and expensive. The demand for superior graphene and intricate fabrication methods may restrict the scalability of these materials. It is imperative to develop cost-effective and scalable synthesis methods that do not compromise photocatalytic performance. Future research may investigate alternate,

environmentally sustainable synthesis methods or the utilization of more cost-effective graphene derivatives to enhance the accessibility and applicability of these materials. Unquestionably, these composites will be highly helpful in photocatalysis, and significant advancements can be anticipated in the future if the constraints are gradually overcome.

Author Contributions

Baji Baba Shaik: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Software and Writing—original draft. **Naresh Kumar Katari:** Validation, Supervision and Writing—review & editing. **Jayaprakash Kanijam Raghupathi:** Data curation and formal analysis. **Surjyakanta Rana:** Visualization, Resources, and Writing—original draft. **Sreekantha B Jonnalagadda:** Funding acquisition, Project administration and Writing—review & editing. All authors reviewed the manuscript.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

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